

Effect of potassium ion on switching of photoinduced electron transfer in inclusion dyads formed by crown ether-porphyrins and an ammonium cation-fullerene[†]

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Abstract : Reversible switching of electron transfer paths in supramolecular donor-acceptor dyads formed by complexing benzo-18-crown-6 appended porphyrins and fulleropyrrolidine appended with an alkyl ammonium ion is demonstrated. The intra-supramolecular to intermolecular switching is achieved by the addition of K^+ which dissociates the crown ether-alkyl ammonium complex, while intermolecular to intra-supramolecular switching was achieved by the addition of 18-crown-6 to extract the potassium ions of the porphyrin-crown entity. The employed porphyrin-fullerene donor-acceptor pairs were proved to be especially suitable for the generation of relatively long-lived charge-separated states which allows easy observation of switching and monitoring of such processes. In the absence of K^+ , the charge-separation takes place within the inclusion complex via the excited singlet state, generating the radical ion pair with the lifetime of 20–60 ns. On addition of K^+ , the inclusion complexes between the porphyrins and C_{60} moieties are dissociated, favoring intermolecular electron transfer via the excited triplet state. Further addition of benzo-18-crown-6 to the solution extracts the K^+ from the crown-ether appended porphyrin and regenerates the inclusion complex with the functionalized fullerene capable of undergoing intra-complex charge separation. The observed phenomena afford concerted metal ion sensing with photoinduced electron transfer in inclusion complexes.

Keywords : Sensor, porphyrin, fullerene, photoinduced electron transfer, laser flash photolysis.

Introduction

Photoinduced electron transfer in donor-acceptor systems is one of the fast growing areas of research driven primarily by solar energy harvesting applications¹⁻³. Among the donor-acceptor systems, porphyrin-fullerene systems are one of the widely studied classes of compounds due to their rich photo- and redox chemistry^{4,5}. In this regard, non-covalently linked via hydrogen bonds, van der Waals forces, electrostatic interactions, π - π stacking or metal-ligand coordination systems have been elegantly designed and widely studied^{4,5}. Fullerenes, owing to their spherical geometry require small reorganization energy in electron transfer reactions⁶. Consequently,

fullerenes involved in donor-acceptor systems accelerate forward the charge separation (k_{CS}) and slow down the charge recombination (k_{CR}), resulting in the formation of long-lived charge-separated (CS) states⁷.

In the case of supramolecular porphyrin-fullerene systems, both intra- and intermolecular type interactions play important role in governing the photochemical reaction pathways⁵. Recently, we devised different supramolecular binding approaches to form porphyrin-fullerene conjugates (MP- C_{60}) held by non-covalent binding interactions thereby achieving control over the molecular structure and topology⁵. In one such approach, by utilizing

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C_{60} functionalized with an alkyl ammonium cation ($C_{60}-NH_3^+$) and crown ether appended porphyrin (Crown-MP; $M = Zn, H_2$) self-assembled inclusion complexes of the type $C_{60}-NH_3^+ : Crown-ZnP$ were formed⁸. In these inclusion systems, owing to higher sensitivity to the additives, it was possible to observe drastic changes in the photochemical/photophysical processes. In the subsequent studies, further extension of building the inclusion complexes by utilizing $C_{60}-NH_3^+$ and Crown-MP bearing crown ether voids at different positions of the macrocycle periphery was accomplished⁹.

As an application point of view, we previously reported switching of electron transfer events in $C_{60}-NH_3^+ : Crown-ZnP$ inclusion complexes formed between 1 and 2 (see Scheme 1 for structures)¹⁰. We have now expanded this study by involving Crown-ZnP of the type 3 and 4 shown in Scheme 1. Between 2 and 3, the difference in the position of the crown ether entity can be seen; that is, for 2, the crown ether is almost perpendicular with respect to the porphyrin plane, whereas for 3, the crown ether is the same porphyrin plane. For 4, four crown ether entities at the same plane with respect to the porphyrin are available which would provide an opportu-

nity to verify how many $C_{60}-NH_3^+$ are effectively needed to observe efficient electron transfer.

Further, switching of intra-supramolecular electron transfer to intermolecular electron transfer in the studied donor-acceptor dyads has been achieved by the addition of K^+ ¹⁰. Because of the replacement of the alkyl ammonium ion inserted in the crown ether by K^+ , intra-supramolecular electron transfer between Crown-ZnP and $C_{60}-NH_3^+$ becomes less efficient by dissociation of the $C_{60}-NH_3^+ : Crown-ZnP$ inclusion complex as shown by step-2 in Scheme 2. Interestingly, when K^+ is extracted by the addition of 18-crown-6 to the solution, switching of intermolecular process to intra-supramolecular process is re-established as shown by step-3 in Scheme 2. In the present study, we try to reveal the following important factors; (i) the binding of the crown ether entities of the donor porphyrin (Crown-ZnP) to the acceptor fullerene ($C_{60}-NH_3^+$) leading to intra-supramolecular photochemical charge-separation, (ii) the switching of the electron transfer from an intra-supramolecular path to intermolecular path upon K^+ inclusion into the crown ether voids, and (iii) extraction of K^+ by the addition of crown ether (step-4) to establish intra-supramolecular charge-separation path.

Scheme 1. Structure of alkylammonium functionalized fullerene ($C_{60}-NH_3^+$, 1) crown-ether appended porphyrins (Crown-ZnP, 2-4) employed to form self-assembled inclusion complexes in the present study.

Scheme 2. Structure of benzo-18-crown-6 appended porphyrin (3) and its binding to $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ (1), and K^+ and 18-crown-6 induced reversible switching between intermolecular electron transfer and intra-supramolecular charge separation.

Results and discussion

Steady-state absorption and fluorescence spectral studies : The steady-state absorption of the Crown-ZnP exhibited an intense Soret band around 420 nm and four less intense visible bands in the 500–700 nm region, respectively^{8a}. No apparent absorption band corresponding to the crown ether entities was observed in the wavelength region covering 350–700 nm. Addition of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ (1) to a solution containing Crown-ZnP (2-4) showed small spectral changes in the ZnP band position and intensity, although the evaluation of the formation constants between $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ and Crown-ZnP was difficult.

On the other hand, the fluorescence intensity changes of Crown-ZnP upon the addition of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ were appreciable. As shown in Fig. 1, two fluorescence bands of 4 ($M = H_2$) around 652 and 720 nm decreased by the addition of 1 until about a half due to formation of assembled porphyrin-fullerene dyad (plots i and ii). Further, addition of K^+ recovered the quenched fluorescence (plot iii and iv), indicating the dissociation of the assembled porphyrin-fullerene dyad due to the replacement

of the ammonium cation attached to fullerene, $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ with the inclusion of K^+ . The complexed K^+ can be removed by the addition of 18-crown-6, resulting in

Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectral changes of 4(H_2) observed with additives in PhCN; $\lambda_{ex} = 560$ nm. (i) 4(H_2), (ii) 4(H_2) + 1, (iii) 4(H_2) + 1 + K^+ (1.0 mM), (iv) 4(H_2) + 1 + K^+ (10 mM) and (v) 4(H_2) + 1 + K^+ + 18-crown-6 in PhCN; concentrations, 1 = 0.11 mM, 4(H_2) = 0.1 mM, and 18-crown-6 = 10 mM.

fluorescence quenching as a consequence of C_{60} - NH_3^+ :Crown-ZnP formation (plot v).

The binding constants (K) of the self-assembled dyads were evaluated by the overall fluorescence quenching behavior by constructing Benesi-Hildebrand plots¹¹. The K values for Crown- $H_2P(2-3)$ binding to C_{60} - NH_3^+ were estimated to be 2000–5000 M^{-1} . For Crown- $H_2P(4)$, slightly larger K value of 6000 M^{-1} was evaluated on assuming 1 : 1 composition, revealing moderately stable self-assembly. For Crown-ZnP(2-3), the K values of 13000–1600 M^{-1} were estimated, suggesting relatively better binding ability of Crown-ZnP(2-3) than Crown- $H_2P(2-3)$.

Electrochemical studies and electron transfer driving forces : Cyclic voltammetric studies were performed to evaluate the redox potentials of the dyads. The free-base porphyrins revealed the first one-electron oxidation (E_{Ox}) corresponding to the formation of Crown- $H_2P^{•+}$ at 0.52 V and the first one-electron reduction corresponding to the formation of Crown- $H_2P^{•-}$ at -1.65 V vs ferrocene/ferrocene⁺ (Fc/Fc⁺) (Fig. 2). Upon forming the dyad by the addition of equal amounts of C_{60} - NH_3^+ , the E_{Ox} wave of Crown- H_2P experienced cathodic shift of 10 mV. Under these conditions, the potential corresponding to the reduction (E_{Red}) of $C_{60}^{•-}$ - NH_3^+ appeared at -1.10 V vs Fc/Fc⁺ was slightly different from that of unbound $C_{60}^{•-}$ - NH_3^+ . Similar electrochemical behavior was observed for other investigated complexes with E_{Ox} of ZnP located in the range 0.27–0.30 V vs Fc/Fc⁺.

The free-energy changes for charge separation (ΔG_{CS})

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of (a) $3(H_2)$; 0.1 mM and (b) 1 (0.11 mM) + $3(H_2)$ in $(n-Bu)_4NClO_4$ (0.1 M) containing PhCN. Scan rate = 100 $mV s^{-1}$.

and charge recombination (ΔG_{CR}) were calculated using the E_{Ox} of Crown-MP(2-4), the E_{Red} of C_{60} - NH_3^+ , singlet excitation energy of Crown-MP(2-4), and the Coulomb energy according to Weller's approach¹². The ΔG_{CS} for both 1:2(H_2) and 1:4(H_2) via the singlet excited states of free-base porphyrin and ΔG_{CS} for both $1^{•-}$:2(H_2)^{•+} and $1^{•-}$:4(H_2)^{•+} were found to be exothermic with values ranging from -0.45 and -1.48 eV in PhCN, respectively. Similarly, for 1:2(Zn) and 1:4(Zn), ΔG_{CS} and ΔG_{CR} are found to be -0.40 and -1.40 eV in PhCN. These negative ΔG_{CS} values indicate that the CS process is fast probably near the top region of the Marcus parabola¹³, since the re-organization energy of the fullerene derivatives was evaluated to be ca. 0.5 eV⁶. On the other hand, the ΔG_{CR} values suggest that the charge-recombination process is slow because of the deep inverted region of the Marcus parabola^{6,13}.

Pico-second time-resolved emission studies : Fig. 3 shows the fluorescence decay time profile of $3(H_2)$ in the absence and presence of C_{60} - NH_3^+ , K^+ and 18-crown-6. The lifetime of the singlet excited state of $3(H_2)$ in the absence of 1 was found to be 9.6 ns by curve-fitting the fluorescence time profile (curve-i) with mono-exponential decay. Addition of 1.1 equivalents of C_{60} - NH_3^+ to the Crown-MPs caused rapid fluorescence decay as shown in curve-ii (Fig. 3). The porphyrin fluorescence decay in the dyad could be curve-fitted satisfactorily by a bi-exponential function. The short lifetime of Crown- H_2P is predominantly due to CS within the supra-molecular dyad in polar PhCN, whereas longer lifetime component is attributed to the un-complexed porphyrin fluorescence.

In the case of 4 having 4 crown ethers, fluorescence

Fig. 3. Fluorescence decays for (i) $3(H_2)$, (ii) 1 + $3(H_2)$, (iii) 1 + $3(H_2)$ + K^+ (1.0 mM), (iv) 1 + $3(H_2)$ + K^+ (10 mM) and (v) 1 + $3(H_2)$ + K^+ + 18-crown-6; 1 = 0.11 mM, $3(H_2)$ = 0.10 mM and 18-crown-6 = 10 mM in PhCN.

time profiles obtained on addition of one to 4 equivalents of **1** are shown in Fig. 4. On increasing addition of **1**, the short fluorescence lifetimes and their fractions were almost the same within the experimental and estimation errors, suggesting that inclusion of one equivalent of **1** saturates the porphyrin quenching process and the additional fullerene entities exhibit little or no effect.

Fig. 4. Fluorescence decays of 4(Zn) (0.1 mM) on (a) 0.0, (b) 0.11, (c) 0.21, (d) 0.31 and (e) 0.42 mM addition of **1** in benzonitrile; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 410$ nm. Fluorescence lifetimes were obtained by curve-fitting and were found to be (a) 1950 ps (100%), (b) 370 ps (65%), (c) 360 ps (62%), (d) 350 ps (63%) and (e) 390 ps (68%), respectively, for the initial part of the decay curve.

Nanosecond transient absorption studies : Transient absorption spectra recorded after 550 nm laser irradiation of Crown-MPs, **2-4** revealed absorption peaks at 820 nm corresponding to the excited triplet state of porphyrins¹⁴. Fullerene, **1** showed a band at 700 nm corresponding to its excited triplet state¹⁴. Fig. 5 shows the transient absorption spectra of $\text{C}_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$:Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$ dyad at different time-intervals. In these spectra, a peak at 1020 nm corresponding to the formation of fulleropyrrolidine anion radical was observed as an experimental proof for the charge-separation mechanism, in addition to the triplet states of the uncomplexed **1** and Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$. Inseted time profile at 1000 nm shows the quick rise within the laser-light pulse width (6 ns) and fast decay within 200 ns followed by the slow decay persisting beyond 1000 ns. The quick rise may correspond to the fluorescence decay within 1 ns, supporting the charge-separation via the singlet excited state of the porphyrin within the inclusion complex. The fast decay of

I^* at 1000 nm corresponds to the charge-recombination with the counter radical cation Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)^{\bullet+}$ within

Fig. 5. Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of **1** (0.11 mM) + Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$ (0.10 mM) after the 532 nm laser irradiation in Ar-saturated PhCN; (O) shows spectrum at 100 ns of $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$. Inset : Time profiles at 1020 nm.

the inclusion complex. The lifetime of the charge separated state was evaluated to be 60 ns.

In order to investigate the K^+ addition effect on the charge-separation, we observed the transient absorption spectra on addition of excess K^+ to the $\text{C}_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$:Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$ inclusion complex (Fig. 6). The 1000 nm band

Fig. 6. Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of **1** (0.11 mM) + Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$ (0.10 mM) + excess K^+ (10 mM) after the 532 nm laser irradiation in Ar-saturated PhCN. Inset : Time profiles at 1020 nm; (i) **1** + Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$ + K^+ (10 mM) and (ii) **1** + Crown- $\text{H}_2\text{P}(2)$.

disappeared leaving the absorption bands of the triplet states of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ and Crown- $H_2P(2)$ at 740 nm and 820 nm as shoulder, respectively, suggesting that the $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(2)$ inclusion complex was destroyed by the K^+ , in agreement with the recovery of the fluorescence decay, prohibiting the charge-separation via the singlet excited state of Crown- H_2P within the $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(2)$. The inserted time profile-i in the presence of excess K^+ shows only small quick rise-quick decay comparing with time profile-ii, suggesting that a small amount of the inclusion complex remains, whereas the high intensity of the slow decay indicates the presence of significant amounts of the triplet states of the uncomplexed components.

In order to investigate the composition of the $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(4)$ inclusion complex, we observed the transient absorption spectra on changing the composition of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ with respect to Crown- $H_2P(4)$. Fig. 7 shows the transient absorption spectra of the solution containing 1 : 1 composition of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(4)$. The 1000 nm band appeared supporting the formation of $C_{60}^{\bullet-}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(4)^{\bullet+}$. The 1000 nm band decays within 100 ns, leaving the absorption bands of the triplet states of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ and Crown- $H_2P(4)$ at 740 nm and 820 nm as shoulder, respectively.

Fig. 7. Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ (0.11 mM) + Crown- $H_2P(4)$ (0.10 mM) after the 532 nm laser irradiation in Ar-saturated PhCN; (○) shows spectrum at 100 ns of $H_2P(4)$. Inset : Time profiles at 1020 nm.

Upon addition of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ up to two equivalents with respect Crown- $ZnP(4)$, the triplet bands of the uncomplexed fullerene increased as shown in Fig. 8. The tails of these triplet absorptions extending to 1000 nm region covered the 1020 nm band, suggesting that the second $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ does not improve the overall efficiency of charge separation. The inserted time profile in the presence of excess $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ shows only small quick rise-quick decay comparing with long time decaying part due to the triplet states of the uncomplexed excess $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$.

Fig. 8. Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ (0.20 mM) + Crown- $ZnP(4)$ (0.10 mM) after the 532 nm laser irradiation in Ar-saturated PhCN. Inset : Time profiles at 1000 nm.

For other inclusion complexes, similar transient spectra and time profiles were obtained, from which the charge-recombination rate constants and the lifetimes of the radical ion pairs (RIP) were evaluated as listed in Table 1. The stabilization of the charge-separated state in these dyads depends upon the nature of the porphyrin and the resulting complex; that is, the stabilization of the charge-separated state for the $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(4)$ dyad was slightly better than that of the $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(2)$ or $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P(3)$ dyads. The τ_{RIP} values obtained for the $C_{60}^{\bullet-}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}ZnP^{\bullet+}$ RIPs were longer than those of the $C_{60}^{\bullet-}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-}H_2P^{\bullet+}$ RIPs, because the stabilization of the RIPs brings to the deep inverted region of the Marcus parabola¹².

Table 1. Rate constants (k_{CR}) and lifetimes (τ_{RIP}) of $(C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-MP^{*+})$ in Ar-saturated PhCN at room temperature

$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-MP^{*+}$	$k_{CR}, s^{-1,c}$	τ_{RIP}, ns	Ref.
$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-H_2P^{*+}(2)$	1.8×10^7	60	10
$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-ZnP^{*+}(2)$	1.0×10^7	100	8a
$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-H_2P^{*+}(3)$	4.1×10^7	30	This work
$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-ZnP^{*+}(3)$	4.9×10^6	200	8a
$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-H_2P^{*+}(4)$	6.9×10^6	150	This work
$C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-ZnP^{*+}(4)$	1.2×10^7	80	8a

Effect of added K^+ and benzo-18-crown-6 on the lifetimes of the dyads : As evidenced by the ns-transient absorption spectra and time profiles, the CS takes place via the singlet excited state of the Crown-MPs, supporting that the fluorescence quenching of the Crown-MP is attributed to the CS process. Thus, the charge-separated rates (k_{CS}^S) were evaluated from the short τ_f components of the inclusion complexes as listed in Table 2 (see footnote for relevant equations). Higher values of k_{CS}^S were

Table 2. Fluorescence lifetime (τ_f), charge-separation rate-constant (k_{CS}^S), increment of complex fraction (Δ) for the investigated $C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-MP$ conjugates in the presence of K^+ and benzo-18-crown-6 in PhCN

Complex ^a	K^+ (1st) mM	Crown mM	K^+ (2nd) mM	τ_f, ns	k_{CS}^{Sb}, s^{-1}	Complexed $\Delta, \%^c$
1:2(H_2)	0	0	0	0.55 (37%) 6.85 (63%)	1.7×10^9	Std
	1.0	0	0	0.73 (12%)	1.3×10^9	-25
	1.0	10	0	0.64 (31%)	1.5×10^9	+19
	1.0	10	>10	2.00 (10%)	3.8×10^8	-21
	1.0	10	0	0.33 (82%) 1.27 (18%)	2.6×10^9	Std
1:2(Zn)	0	0	0	0.44 (60%)	1.8×10^9	-22
	1.0	10	0	0.36 (80%)	2.3×10^9	+20
	1.0	10	>10	0.73 (25%)	8.7×10^8	-55
	1.0	10	0	0.65 (48%) 6.82 (52%)	1.4×10^9	Std
	1.0	0	0	0.70 (40%)	1.3×10^9	-8
1:3(H_2)	0	0	0	0.68 (43%)	1.4×10^9	+3
	1.0	10	>10	1.40 (20%)	6.0×10^8	-22
	1.0	0	0	0.32 (57%) 1.52 (43%)	2.6×10^9	Std
	1.0	0	0	0.44 (45%)	1.8×10^9	-12
	1.0	10	0	0.38 (50%)	2.0×10^9	+5
1:3(Zn)	0	0	0	0.80 (27%) 0.67 (40%) 6.40 (60%)	7.5×10^8	-23
	1.0	0	0	0.80 (30%)	1.1×10^9	-10
	1.0	10	0	0.70 (38%)	1.3×10^9	+8
	1.0	0	>10	4.10 (25%)	1.3×10^8	-13
	1.0	0	0	0.37 (65%) 1.52 (35%)	2.2×10^9	Std
1:4(H_2)	0	0	0	0.70 (50%)	9.3×10^8	-15
	1.0	10	0	0.40 (64%)	2.0×10^9	+14
	1.0	10	>10	1.50 (45%)	1.7×10^8	-19
	1.0	0	0	0.80 (30%)	1.1×10^9	-10
	1.0	10	0	0.70 (38%)	1.3×10^9	+8
1:4(Zn)	0	0	0	4.10 (25%)	1.3×10^8	-13
	1.0	0	0	0.37 (65%) 1.52 (35%)	2.2×10^9	Std
	1.0	0	0	0.70 (50%)	9.3×10^8	-15
	1.0	10	0	0.40 (64%)	2.0×10^9	+14
	1.0	10	>10	1.50 (45%)	1.7×10^8	-19

^aComplex refers to $C_{60}^{*-}NH_3^+ : Crown-MP$ wherein the concentrations of the species are held at 0.11 mM and 0.10 mM, respectively.

^b $k_{CS}^S = (1/\tau_f)_{complex} - (1/\tau_f)_{uncomplex}$.

^cComplexed Δ (+) and uncomplexed Δ (-) compared with immediate upper value.

obtained for the dyads indicating the occurrence of efficient electron transfer.

The first addition of K^+ switches the occurrence of electron transfer route from intra-inclusion complex to intermolecular electron transfer (Scheme 2) by replacing $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ in Crown-MPs with K^+ , thus, decreasing the fraction of the fast fluorescence decaying part (step-2 in Scheme 2). On further addition of excess of 18-crown-6, switching of the electron transfer route from intermolecular to intra-inclusion complex (step-3 in Scheme 2) is re-established, since the K^+ is captured by the added benzo-18-crown-6, thus re-accelerating the fluorescence decay (step-4 in Scheme 2). This observation indicates that the addition of excess 18-crown-6 eliminates most of K^+ in the cavity of Crown-MPs in the supramolecular dyad with $C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+$ and changes the electron transfer path from intermolecular to intra-supramolecular. That is, successful switching of the electron-transfer path of the supramolecular dyads by the insertion and the elimination of K^+ is observed.

In Table 2, the first addition of one equivalent K^+ to ($C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-MP}(2)$) decreases the inclusion complex by 20%, whereas about 10% decrease was observed for ($C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-MP}(3)$) and ($C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-MP}(4)$), suggesting most weak inclusion complex for Crown-MP(2), because of perpendicular orientation of the crown ether with respect to the porphyrin plane. The rate constants of the CS within the remaining inclusion complexes are almost the same as the original ones without the presence of one equivalent K^+ . The highest recovery of the inclusion complex by the external addition of crown ether was also observed for Crown-MP(2), suggesting that the included K^+ is most easily extracted from the perpendicular Crown-MP. The second addition of K^+ in excess to ($C_{60}\text{-NH}_3^+:\text{Crown-MP}(2)$) destroyed the inclusion complex again by 20–55%, resulting in slowing down the CS process of the remaining inclusion complexes, which suggests the alternation of the structures of inclusion complexes in the presence of excess K^+ and external crown ether.

Summary

Control over the formation of the supramolecular inclusion complexes between the alkyl ammonium functionalized fullerene and the crown ether appended porphyrins by the addition of the K^+ and external crown ether is established. The formation of the inclusion complexes induces charge separation via the singlet excited state of the porphyrin moiety with light excitation as evi-

denced by the fluorescence quenching and radical ion pair formation proved by the transient absorption technique. The addition of the K^+ tends to destroy the complexes by replacing the ammonium functionalized fullerene in the crown ether with K^+ , leaving the inclusion complexes presenting as equilibrium. Under these conditions only intermolecular electron transfer could be observed. Further addition of external crown ether regenerates the inclusion complex with the ammonium functionalized fullerene by extracting the bound K^+ . The regenerated inclusion complexes exhibit fast charge separation where the rates are in the range similar to the original ones, thus proving the reversibility of the path of photochemical events.

Experimental

Materials : The syntheses and characterization of the crown ether appended free-base porphyrins and fullerene derivative are given elsewhere^{8,10}. The compounds were purified freshly prior to the spectral and photochemical measurements. All the chromatographic materials and solvents were procured from Fisher Scientific and were used as received. Tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate, ($n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$)₄NClO₄ was from Fluka Chemicals. All other chemicals utilized in the synthesis were from Aldrich Chemicals (Milwaukee, WI) and were used as received.

Instrumentation : The UV-Visible spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu Model 1600 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The fluorescence emission was monitored by using a Spex Fluorolog-tau spectrometer. Right angle method was utilized. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded on a EG&G Model 263A potentiostat using a three electrode system. A platinum button or glassy carbon electrode was used as the working electrode. A platinum wire served as the counter electrode and a Ag/AgCl was used as the reference electrode. Ferrocene/ferrocenium redox couple was used as an internal standard. All the solutions were purged prior to electrochemical and spectral measurements using argon gas.

Time-resolved emission and transient absorption measurements : The picosecond time-resolved fluorescence spectra were measured using an argon-ion pumped Ti:sapphire laser (Tsunami) and a streak scope (Hamamatsu Photonics). The details of the experimental setup are described elsewhere^{14,15}. Nanosecond transient absorption spectra in the NIR region were measured by means of laser-flash photolysis; 532 nm light from a Nd:YAG laser was used as the exciting source and a Ge-

avalanche-photodiode module was used for detecting the monitoring light from a pulsed Xe-lamp as described in our previous report^{14,15}.

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References

- (a) J. S. Connolly and J. R. Bolton, in : "Photoinduced Electron Transfer", eds. M. A. Fox and M. Chanon, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1988, Part D, pp. 303-393; (b) J. R. Winkler and H. B. Gray, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 369; (c) C. Kirmaier and D. Holton, in : "The Photosynthetic Reaction Center", eds. J. Deisenhofer and J. R. Norris, Academic Press, San Diego, 1993, Vol. II, pp. 49-70.
- (a) M. R. Wasielewski, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 435; (b) H. Kurreck and M. Huber, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1995, **34**, 849; (c) J. S. Sessler, B. Wang, S. L. Springs and C. T. Brown, "Comprehensive Supramolecular Chemistry", eds. J. L. Atwood, J. E. D. Davies, D. D. MacNicol and F. Vögtle, Pergamon, 1996, Chapt. 9; (d) T. Hayashi and H. Ogoshi, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1997, **26**, 355; (e) M. W. Ward, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1997, **26**, 365.
- (a) A. Osuka, N. Mataga and T. Okada, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1997, **69**, 797; (b) N. Mataga and H. Miyasaka, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **107**, 431; (c) M.-J. Blanco, M. C. Jiménez, J.-C. Chambron, V. Heitz, M. Linke and J.-P. Sauvage, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1999, **28**, 293; (d) D. Gust, T. A. Moore and A. L. Moore, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2001, **34**, 40; (e) "Electron Transfer in Chemistry", ed. V. Balzani, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2001.
- (a) M. Prato, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 1997, **7**, 1097; (b) H. Imahori and Y. Sakata, *Adv. Mater.*, 1997, **9**, 537; (c) N. Martín, L. Sánchez, B. Illescas and I. Pérez, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 2527; (d) F. Diederich and M. Gómez-López, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1999, **28**, 263; (e) D. M. Guldi and M. Prato, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **33**, 695; (f) D. M. Guldi, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2002, **31**, 22; (g) H. Imahori and S. Fukuzumi, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2004, **14**, 525; (h) L. Sanchez, N. Martin and D. M. Guldi, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 5374.
- (a) M. E. El-Khouly, O. Ito, P. M. Smith and F. D'Souza, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. C*, 2004, **5**, 79; (b) F. D'Souza and O. Ito, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **249**, 1410; (c) F. D'Souza and O. Ito, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 4913.
- (a) H. Imahori, K. Hagiwara, T. Akiyama, M. Akoi, S. Taniguchi, T. Okada, M. Shirakawa and Y. Sakata, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, **263**, 545; (b) D. M. Guldi and K.-D. Asmus, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 5744; (c) H. Imahori, M. E. El-Khouly, M. Fujitsuka, O. Ito, Y. Sakata and S. Fukuzumi, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 325.
- (a) H. Imahori, K. Yamada, M. Hasegawa, S. Taniguchi, T. Okada and Y. Sakata, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1997, **36**, 2626; (b) C. Luo, D. M. Guldi, H. Imahori, K. Tamaki and Y. Sakata, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 6535; (c) H. Imahori, K. Tamaki, Y. Araki, Y. Sekiguchi, O. Ito, Y. Sakata and S. Fukuzumi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 5165; (d) T. J. Kesti, N. V. Tkachenko, V. Vehmanen, H. Yamada, H. Imahori, S. Fukuzumi and H. Lemmetyinen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 8067; (e) N. Watanabe, N. Kihara, Y. Furusho, T. Takata, Y. Araki and O. Ito, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 681; (f) F. D'Souza, P. M. Smith, M. E. Zandler, A. L. McCarty, M. Itou, Y. Araki and O. Ito, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 7898; (g) G. de la Torre, F. Giacalone, J. L. Segura, N. Martín and D. M. Guldi, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2005, **11**, 1267; (h) N. Sollaadié, M. E. Walthers, H. Herschbach, E. Leize, A.V. Dorsselaer, T. M. Figueira Duarte and J.-F. Nierengarten, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **62**, 1979.
- (a) F. D'Souza, R. Chitta, S. Gadde, P. A. Karr, M. E. Zandler, A. L. McCarty, A. S. D. Sandanayaka, Y. Araki and O. Ito, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2005, **11**, 4416; (b) F. D'Souza, R. Chitta, S. Gadde, A. L. McCarty, P. A. Karr, M. E. Zandler, A. S. D. Sandanayaka, Y. Araki and O. Ito, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2006, **110**, 5905.
- (a) F. D'Souza, R. Chitta, S. Gadde, M. E. Zandler, A. S. D. Sandanayaka, Y. Araki and O. Ito, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 1279; (b) F. D'Souza, R. Chitta, S. Gadde, M. E. Zandler, A. L. McCarty, A. S. D. Sandanayaka, Y. Araki and O. Ito, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2006, **110**, 4338.
- A. S. D. Sandanayaka, Y. Araki, O. Ito, R. Chitta, S. Gadde and F. D'Souza, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, 4327.
- H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
- (a) D. Rehm and A. Weller, *Isr. J. Chem.*, 1970, **7**, 259; (b) N. Mataga and H. Miyasaka, "Electron Transfer", eds. J. Jortner and M. Bixon, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1999, Part 2, pp. 431-496.
- (a) R. A. Marcus and N. Sutin, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1985, **811**, 265; (b) R. A. Marcus, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1993, **32**, 1111; (c) M. Bixon and J. Jortner, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **106**, 35.
- (a) Y. Araki and O. Ito, in : "Handbook of Organic Electronics and Photonics", ed. H. S. Nalwa, Vol. 2, American Scientific Publishers, California, 2008, Chapt. 12, pp. 473-513; (b) Y. Araki and O. Ito, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. C : Photochem. Rev.*, 2008, **9**, 93.
- (a) H. N. Ghosh, H. Pal, A. V. Sapre and J. P. Mittal, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 11722; (b) T. Nojiri, A. Watanabe and O. Ito, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1998, **102**, 5215.

